

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Study of Displacement Damage Effects on Optocouplers with Proton Radiation (DIDOP)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA06-136
General application	<i>Space and harsh environment</i>
Type of test	TNID
Group leader, Institute	<i>Yolanda Morilla, Centro Nacional de Aceleradores (CNA)</i>
Dates of the experiment	<i>22nd – 24th February, 2023</i>
Facility	<i>PARTREC facility</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>25 hours</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The Spanish National Accelerators Centre (Centro Nacional de Aceleradores) and the company ALTER Technology are leading a new study about radiation effects on optocouplers, with the technical support of principal optoelectronic manufactures, the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) and the European Space Agency (ESA).

In general, optoelectronic components are very radiation-sensitive devices. Despite this risk, optocouplers are essential components used to minimize noise and Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) by isolating noise between circuits and subsystems. Their use in space and harsh environments represents a challenge and therefore a clear motivation for this work. Although this family of devices has been studied over the years, new non-tested technologies are being more and more demanded.

The purpose of this project is to evaluate the main radiation effects on a representative set of optocouplers, selecting the more used and/or emerging components. The study will be accomplished in different blocks, with the following specific objectives:

- To characterize the Total Ionizing Dose (TID), Displacement Damage (DD), and Single Event Transients (SET) effects on the most relevant and/or more highly demanded optocouplers for the space industry and harsh environments.
- To explore synergistic effects and assess the applicability of the conventionally used Non-ionizing Energy Loss (NIEL) scaling for these components.
- To include the test results in our database, PRECEDER, and analyze following our methodology to compare the new results with the corresponding archival data.

This campaign, corresponding to the RADNEXT TA06-136, is a continuation of our previous neutron test campaign. We have focused here on the study of the degradation of the main electrical parameters of several sets of optocouplers using a monoenergetic proton beam, using different energies. Although 20, 60 and 190 MeV proton experiments were scheduled, only 62 MeV and 184 MeV were finally achieved.

Experiment test report

Due to the time limitations to perform every campaign, first we have selected the same 15 different part types used in the last neutron test campaign, and two new references, from different manufacturers collaborating in the project. For each part type, a total of 5 samples were irradiated and one more was considered as a control reference.

The devices were distributed on two irradiation boards. These were designed so that the components were placed in a 10x10 cm² surface to use the maximum homogeneous size of the proton beam available at the facility (**Figure 1**). To maximize the given beam time for testing, one board was irradiated while the electrical characterization, on the second board devices, was done. The distribution in the specific manufactured sample holder can be also seen in the figure, when it was placed in the facility positioning frame.

Figure 1

Below is a summary of the test campaign:

The **Table 1** shows the part types under test during this campaign, along with relevant information about manufacture, functionality, package, and the external view of each device.

Table I

DUT	Manufacture	Functionality	Package	External view
HCPL-5230	BROADCOM	Hermetically Sealed, Low IF, Wide VCC, Logic Gate Optocoupler	Hermetic DIP-8	
OLS-600	SKYWORKS	Hermetic Surface Mount, High-Speed Schmitt Trigger Optocoupler	Hermetic LCC-6	
IBS-249	ISOBAUD	Radiation Tolerant Phototransistor Hermetic Surface Mount Optocoupler	Hermetic LCC-6	
HCPL-5530	BROADCOM	Hermetically Sealed, Transistor Output Optocoupler for Analog and Digital Application	Hermetic DIP-8	
OLS-300	SKYWORKS	Hermetic Surface Mount High-Speed Optocoupler	Hermetic LCC-6	
4N38M	ONSEMI	6-Pin DIP High Voltage Phototransistor Optocoupler	PDIP-6	
SFH-601-3	VISHAY	Optocoupler, Phototransistor Output, with Base Connection	PDIP-6	
IBS-300	ISOBAUD	Radiation Tolerant High-Speed 1MHz Hermetic Surface Mount Optocoupler	Hermetic LCC-6	
HCPL-5730	BROADCOM	Hermetically Sealed, Low IF, Wide VCC, High Gain Optocoupler	Hermetic DIP-8	

OLF-400	SKYWORKS	Low-Input Current Hermetic Surface Mount Optocoupler	Hermetic CFP-8	
TLX-9300	TOSHIBA	TOSHIBA Photocoupler IRLED & Phototransistor	4-PIN SO6	
HCPL-5430	BROADCOM	Hermetically Sealed, Very High- Speed, Logic Gate Optocoupler	Hermetic DIP-8	
OLS-500	SKYWORKS	Hermetic Surface Mount High CMR, High-Speed Logic Gate Optocoupler	Hermetic LCC-6	
IBH-7000	ISOBAUD	Radiation Tolerant Hermetic 8-Pin DIP Linear Optocoupler	Hermetic DIP-8	
HCPL-5630	BROADCOM	Hermetically Sealed, High-Speed, High CMR, Logic Gate Optocoupler	Hermetic DIP-8	
IL300	VISHAY	High Gain Wide Bandwith Optocoupler	DIP-8	
OLH7000	SKYWORKS	Linear Optocoupler	Hermetic DIP-8	

The **Table II** shows the date code, technology and electrical parameters measured during the test. The parameters were measured for each single device after each exposure steps. All the DUTs were unbiased, that is, all the pins connected to ground.

Table II

DUT	Date code	Technology	Electrical parameters
HCPL-5230	2222	AlGaAs (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=8mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL (@IOL=6.4mA) Output leakage current: IOHH1 (@IF=8mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=5.5V) Output leakage current: IOHH2 (@IF=8mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=20V) Low supply current: ICCL1 (@VF1=VF2=0V, VCC=5.5V) Low supply current: ICCL2 (@VF1=VF2=0V, VCC=20V) Low supply current: ICCL3 (@VF1=VF2=8V, VCC=5.5V) Low supply current: ICCL4 (@VF1=VF2=8V, VCC=20V)
OLS-600	1908A	AlGaAs (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL (@IF=10uA, RL=680Ω, VCC=15V) High output current: IOH (@IF=0uA, VCC=VO=15V) Low supply current: ICCL (@IF=5mA, VCC=15V) High supply current: ICCH (@IF=0mA, VCC=15V)
IBS-249	1721	AlGaAs (Led) + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=100uA) Collector-emitter saturation voltage: VCE (sat) (@IF=2mA, IC=2mA) Collector-emitter dark current, off state: ICE_OFF (@VCE=20V) Collector current, on state: IC_ON (@IF=1mA, VCE= 5V)
HCPL-5530	2129	GaAsP (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=20mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) High output current: IOH (@IF=0mA, IF(other channels)=20mA, VCC=VO=18V) Low supply current: ICCL (@IF1=IF2=20mA, VCC=18V) High supply current: ICCH (@IF1=IF2=0mA (all channels), VCC=18V) Current transfer ratio: CTR (@IF=16mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V)
OLS-300	2126	AlGaAs (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL (@IF=10uA, IOL=15mA, VCC=4.5V) High output current: IOH (@IF=0uA, VCC=VO=15V) Low supply current: ICCL (@IF=0mA, VCC=15V, VO open) High supply current: ICCH (@IF=0mA, VCC=15V, VO open) Current transfer ratio: CTR (@IF=10mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V)
4N38M	1815	GaAs (Led) + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Collector dark current: ICEO (@IF=0mA, VCE=60V, No RBE) Collector-emitter saturation voltage: VCE (sat) (@IF=20mA, IC=4mA) Current transfer ratio: CTR (@IF=10mA, VCE=10V)
SFH-601-3	2222	GaAs (Led) + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=60mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Collector dark current: ICEO (@VCE=10V) Collector-emitter saturation voltage: VCE (sat) (@IF=10mA, IC=2.5mA) Current transfer ratio: CTR (@IF=10mA, VCE=5V)

IBS-300	2228	AlGaAs (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL (@IF=10mA, IOL=1.5mA, VCC=4.5V) High output current: IOH (@IF=0uA, VCC=VO=15V) Low supply current: ICCL (@IF=10mA, VCC=15V, VO open) High supply current: ICCH (@IF=0mA, VCC=15V, VO open) Current transfer ratio: CTR (@IF=10mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V)
HCPL-5730	2144	GaAsP (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=1.6mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL1 (@IF=0.5mA, IOL=1.5mA, VCC=4.5V) Low output voltage: VOL2 (@IF=1.6mA, IOL=4.8mA, VCC=4.5V) Low output voltage: VOL3 (@IF=5mA, IOL=10mA, VCC=4.5V) High output current: IOH (@IF=2uA, VCC=VO=18V) Low supply current: ICCL (@IF1=IF2=1.6mA, VCC=18V) High supply current: ICCH (@IF1=IF2=0mA, VCC=18V) Current transfer ratio: CTR1 (@IF=0.5mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V) Current transfer ratio: CTR2 (@IF=1.6mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V) Current transfer ratio: CTR3 (@IF=5mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V)
OLF-400	1510	AlGaAs (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=1.6mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL1 (@IF=0.5mA, IOL=10mA, VCC=4.5V) Low output voltage: VOL2 (@IF=5mA, IOL=10mA, VCC=4.5V) High output current: IOH (@IF=0mA, VCC=VO=18V) Low supply current: ICCL (@IF=1.6mA, VCC=18V) High supply current: ICCH (@IF=0mA, VCC=18V) Current transfer ratio: CTR1 (@IF=0.5mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V) Current transfer ratio: CTR2 (@IF=1.6mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V) Current transfer ratio: CTR3 (@IF=5mA, VCC=4.5V, VO=0.4V)
TLX-9300	2208	GaAlAs (Led) + Bipolar	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Collector dark current: ICEO (@VCE=24V) Collector-emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)1 (@IF=1mA, IC=0.2mA) Collector-emitter saturation voltage: VCE(sat)1 (@IF=8mA, IC=2.4mA) Current transfer ratio: IC/IF (@IF=5mA, VCE=5V) Saturated CTR: IC/IF(sat) (@IF=1mA, VCE= 0.4V)
HCLP-5430	2213	AlGaAs (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL (@IOL=8mA) Output leakage current: IOHH (@VF=0.7V, VO=5.25V) Low supply current: ICCL (@VE=0.7V, VCC=5.25V) High supply current: ICCH (@VE=0.7V, VCC=5.25V)
OLS-500	1945B	AlGaAs (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL (@IF=5mA, IOL=10mA, VCC=5.5V) High output current: IOH (@IF=250uA, VCC=VO=5.5V) Low supply current: ICCL (@IF=5mA, VCC=5.5V) High supply current: ICCH (@IF=0mA, VCC=5.5V)

IBH-7000	1721	LED + PIN	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse voltage: VR (@IR=100uA) Open circuit voltage: VOC (@IF=10mA) Dark current: ID (@IF=0mA, VR=15V) Servo current gain: K1 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V) Forward current gain: K2 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V) Transfer current gain: K3 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V)
HCPL-5630	2222	GaAsP (Led) + Hybrid	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=20mA) Reverse breakdown voltage: VBR (@IR=10uA) Low output voltage: VOL (@IF=10mA, IOL=10mA, VCC=5.5V) Output leakage current: IOH (@IF=250uA, VCC=VO=5.5V) Low supply current: ICCL (@IF1=IF2=0mA, VCC=5.5V) High supply current: ICCH (@IF1=IF2=0mA, VCC=5.5V) Current transfer ratio: hFE CTR (@IF=10mA, VCC=5.5V, VO=0.6V)
IL300	2148	AlGaAs	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse voltage: VR (@IR=1uA) Open circuit voltage: VOC (@IF=10mA) Dark current: IDARK (@IF=0mA, VR=15V) Servo current gain: K1 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V) Forward current gain: K2 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V) Transfer current gain: K3 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V)
OLH7000	N/Av	LED + PIN	Forward voltage: VF (@IF=10mA) Reverse voltage: VR (@IR=100uA) Open circuit voltage: VOC (@IF=10mA) Dark current: IDARK (@IF=0mA, VR=15V) Servo current gain: K1 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V) Forward current gain: K2 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V) Transfer current gain: K3 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V) Servo current: IP1 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V) Forward current: IP2 (@IF=10mA, VDET=-15V)

In the **Table III**, the dosimetry details are presented, as provided by the PARTREC staff.

Table III

Energy (MeV)	Flux (p/cm ² s)	Fluence (p/cm ²)		
		Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
184	4,00E+08	1,10E+11	5,00E+11	1,10E+12
62	4,00E+08	1,10E+11	5,00E+11	1,10E+12

All the devices have shown degradation when exposed to the proton radiation, as expected. However, there are devices that show a higher tolerance to radiation and therefore exhibit lower degradation. In addition, we observe that the degradation due to high energy (184 MeV) is lower than the degradation due to the lower energy (62 MeV). More details and the proper study of the data will be published, when the full analysis is completed, in different journal publications and/or conferences (NSREC, RADECS and IEEE editorials).

The figure below (**Figure II**) shows an example of how the same parameter, measured for two different part types of devices at the same energy (62 MeV) shows a different trend. In this case, the devices named DUT1 are clearly less tolerant to the radiation from the first step fluence.

Figure II

The **Figure III** shows an example of how the same parameter, measured for the same part type shows a different trend due to the energy of the beam. In this case, the devices irradiated at 62 MeV are clearly more sensitive.

Figure III

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008126.